

Administrative Control and Its Relationship to Making Sound Decisions

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Abstract: In this article, we talked about administrative control and its relationship to making sound decisions, as we must be fully aware that administrative control is not understood by some and is interpreted as controlling employee errors and practicing methods of controlling them and killing the creativity and achievements of members of the institution, but it is a means of achieving some kind. organization and effectiveness within the enterprise; Administrative control is the means through which the administrative authorities can know how the work flows within the facility, in order to ensure the correct functioning of the work to achieve the objectives and discover errors, omissions or deviations and work to fix and put them. Take the necessary preventive measures to remove its causes.

Keywords: Administrative control, Make decision.

I. INTRODUCTION

The main function of administrative control is to measure and correct performance in order to ensure that the objectives have been achieved, and that the plans have been properly implemented. Also, the real control is the one that precedes the events and works on alerting to the expected deviations, and preventing them before they occur to be implemented in accordance with the established standards. . Oversight in this sense assures every official that what has been accomplished is what is intended to be accomplished according to the set plan, and that investors and those in charge of financial markets are aware of the reasons behind the different decisions and behaviors of dealers and the factors influencing their investment decisions.

The administrative control process is one of the important and basic functions of the administration, through which we can identify that the work and activities that are implemented are carried out according to what was planned by the administration, and that the modern state has become managed through public utilities that have become the backbone of the life of society, as it performs a lot of services for citizens, so it has become necessary for these institutions to follow clear plans and studies, and it is necessary for the competent authorities to ensure the correctness of the implementation process and adherence to the existing policies and plans, in order to reduce the imbalance and deviation that may affect the stages of administrative work The defect was rectified in a timely manner, while not allowing administrative work to deviate from the boundaries and policies drawn for it, and finding the necessary solutions to the deviations and the reasons that led to that.

Oversight has developed today and has become, in the opinion of management, economic and financial scholars, necessary in any system, as any administrative and material system in which there is no effective and regular oversight is considered an incomplete system that lacks the elements of its existence and contributes to increasing the failure of organizations.

II. What is the relationship between management control and decision-making?

The awareness of investors and those in charge of financial markets of the reasons behind the different decisions and behaviors of dealers and the factors affecting their investment decisions would help raise the level of awareness of the requirements of these markets, and raise their efficiency, and this leads directly or indirectly to an increase in investment awareness, which protects the stock market from the risks of dealing with an inexperienced investor. Just as the trader in the financial market makes a sound decision regarding investment, whether in terms of the decision or timing of buying or selling a particular share, he must be conversant and know how to read the financial

statements, how to analyze these lists, and extract some financial indicators that enable him to Making rational investment decisions, and reducing the level of uncertainty associated with these decisions, which leads to raising the effectiveness and quality of any investment decision through the proper guidance of savings. Also, all investors must be equal in terms of the quantity, type and time of information that is received to them, and only here can justice be achieved in these markets so that they become an appropriate investment climate.

The practice of administrative control is one of the concepts that have a significant impact on the success or failure of any institution, because of the manager's decisive role in directly influencing the behavior of employees, and in generating the motivation towards leadership, as it is an effective investment for the efforts of employees, that is, whenever the manager is able to carry out his tasks And his responsibilities to be able to achieve the desired goals of the institution.

There were many different studies, both foreign and Arab that dealt with the issue of the practice of administrative control, which emphasized its importance and efficiency in the development of various institutions. While others believe that it is important to make changes and developments, as it is time for managers to acquire supervisory management skills; to enhance their business, and keep pace with the requirements of the current era.

Hence, the administrative control is basically related to the elements of the administrative process to each other closely and in an integrative manner, and is mainly related to the planning process, as the control process means a group of works that aims to review what has been done and measure what has been accomplished in comparison with the objectives set by the plans, and from Then take the necessary measures to correct any deviation from the plan. Administrative control is important in most areas, whether in the public or private sector, for several reasons: first, to prevent errors from occurring or recurring, and secondly to ensure the proper progress of work according to what is planned, and thirdly to encourage administrative success.

III. But the question is, what is the benefit gained from integrating administrative control into making sound decisions?

Based on the results of the oversight, the decision maker can issue the necessary decisions to correct the course. If the defect is due to the planning method and the error in estimating and setting goals as if they were subjective or realistic, then he must issue the necessary decisions so that they become realistic decisions and can be implemented, but if the plans are And what it contained of correct and realistic goals and it was proven that the defect is from the subordinates, which requires the superior to take the necessary decisions, whether related to training and rehabilitation of subordinates or the issuance of disciplinary sanctions, as the case may be.

However, if the president finds, through the supervisory reports, that the defect is due to organizational reasons, such as the overlapping of competencies or the lack of sufficient powers commensurate with the responsibilities to be accomplished, then he needs to take organizational decisions to address the organizational defect and gaps.

Hence, the managing director must follow modern management practices, which are among the things that contribute to a state of sustainable leadership that provide future directions for the institution, put it in the circle of local and global competition, and increase the degree of its adaptation to the accelerating and successive changes that include all areas of life, which Making management thought based on diverse skills an important requirement for institutions looking for excellence and advancement, and obtaining a competitive advantage.

As the pursuit of entrepreneurship in business, which has become one of the most important and modern topics in the field of management, and the standards of leadership and creativity have become at the forefront of the goals that institutions seek to achieve to support more excellence and uniqueness in their performance, which requires administrative leaders to make efforts to achieve success and progress by accreditation On speed, flexibility and innovation by adopting management skills practices.

In addition, institutions of all kinds seek to achieve success and leadership in work, and access to this is not easy in light of intense competition. Therefore, it seeks to employ various administrative skills; To achieve success in work, as it is one of the important capabilities of any institution, as it is a vital component, the various dimensions associated with it should be referred to, and this concept has evolved to include management in its various fields.

Hence, the researchers defined the skill in general as a distinct ability that includes accuracy and speed in completing tasks, which enables the individual to practice his work in an easier way than others, and to influence others

to carry out daily work with the behavior of an investor and an employee; To accomplish the tasks entrusted to him and the tasks in order to reach the specified goals.

Accordingly, management skills mean the ability to make the right decisions related to the industry, work to direct and lead employees effectively, and manage the activities of the organization in a way that ensures the achievement of the set goals. These administrative skills include all different human skills, in addition to the cognitive and technical skills necessary to complete the work and complete the company's affairs, which help to motivate employees and influence them positively.

Some indicated that the practices of management skills contribute to directing and organizing the work of others by persuading and leading them towards a certain thing. Others indicated the skills that a person possesses in influencing others; To accomplish the work and accept a law, policy, or idea that aims to achieve the goals to be accomplished, and their ability to identify methods and methods for communicating with workers and influencing them. The primary importance of management is that it is a link between employees and the institution, and it is the most effective way to achieve the goals, mission and vision of the institution in the short and long term.

In view of administrative control and its relationship to administrative decisions, it must be emphasized that researchers may find, by reviewing the supervisory system, that the defect is not due to the previous reasons, but rather to the traditional management style, such as the existence of problems between subordinates themselves or with their boss, so the decision is to send them to specialized courses; To acquaint them with the best way to deal with each other, with an indication of the necessity of adhering to the principles of work.

IV. The question here remains, what are the effects achieved from the relationship of administrative control in making the right decision?

The importance of administrative control stems from the qualities and characteristics possessed by decision makers that enable them to be able to enhance the common vision between him and the workers. To develop innovative methods for solving problems, constantly train them to develop their skills, and motivate them to follow skills that enhance their self-ability, and their ability to identify their strengths and weaknesses, and assign tasks to them based on that, which increases the chance of success for the organization. This relationship is based on a number of basic points:

1- The control function focuses on that the goals and policies that were set during the planning process are accomplished in the way planned during implementation

2- The objectives should be characterized by objectivity and verifiability within the available possibilities.

3- The control process helps the planning person to adjust his plans in proportion to the situations that are revealed during implementation. Hence, it appears that the control function is linked to the planning function in light of the following facts: Oversight tasks cannot be carried out unless there is a specific plan and objectives. Oversight indicates, through the standards that are usually embodied in the planning process, the soundness of implementation of the set plan and the extent of commitment to its implementation. Oversight is not limited to following up the implementation and diagnosing deviations in order to address them, but rather reveals the correctness of the planning process and the policies and procedures that follow, and the ability of the plan to achieve the specified goals.

V. Conclusion

In the previous decades, administrative control witnessed great interest from researchers and thinkers, which led to the emergence of a number of theories and numerous researches on this subject. That is, when plans are developed, they move into implementation, and as they are put among the administrators to be implemented according to the goals set in advance, where the manager directs and trains the workers, and works to accomplish tasks in cooperation and interaction with them, and the manager, through the managerial skills he possesses, motivates them to work and compete, This requires institutions to adopt a variety of skill practices, and to employ managers with superior administrative skills and competencies so that he can lead working individuals towards the desired goal with the necessary efficiency and effectiveness. Hence, the process of integrating administrative control with the guidance process in the following points: First, oversight and through feedback play an important role in the decision-making process, which is the basis of the guidance function. Through the feedback process, managers in decision-making centers can know the results of the work and the various changes that may arise in the working conditions and environment. Secondly, the control and follow-up units in the organization and its departments provide managers with correct and

accurate data and information on an ongoing basis and on the basis of which they make their decisions to complete work and motivate employees.

The relationship of administrative control with administrative functions requires that decision-makers be familiar with administrative skills based on interaction and participation in the activities and work carried out by the institution within arranged steps, and include methods and methods for change, finding a new vision, and making cooperation an institutional work, and that administrative skills constitute one of the important entrances At the present time, and among the basic factors for effective management at various organizational levels, that is, the amount of success of institutions is determined by their administrative efficiency, and the various administrative skills that enhance the capabilities of workers, and to bring about positive changes at work within a clear and understandable vision, and to follow a participatory approach between the manager and the subordinate

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